

MODIFIED CRUCIFORM SPECIMEN FOR BIAXIAL TESTING OF FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

This work introduces an enhanced cruciform specimen optimized for the mechanical characterization of fibre-reinforced composite materials subjected to a biaxial stress state (e.g. orthogonal loads). The tension-tension case, for which there is scarce published data, is specifically analyzed. First, different cruciform specimens reported in literature are modelled via finite elements to determine their stress distribution. Based on these results, as well as in existing standards and guidelines for uniaxial mechanical testing in metals and composites, an enhanced design is developed, aimed to ensure that the deformation field in its central region remains truly biaxial, thus increasing the reliability of yielded data. Future work will cover an extensive experimental program to validate this design, although early results using full-deformation strain field measurements are encouraging.

Keywords: biaxial testing, cruciform specimen, composite materials

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite considerable research in the field, predicting damage in fibre-reinforced composites is still an unresolved problem. This is due to the complexity of the different failure modes exhibited [1], which are not yet completely understood. An added complexity is the little-known interaction between such failure modes [2]. Size effects are also reported to exert a significant influence on testing results [3]. Finally, the lack of standard testing procedures can lead to experimental data which might not represent the desired stress state [4].

Although some failure criteria are successful in capturing one or more failure modes, there are still considerable developments to be made. An obstacle for the development of more advanced theories is the scarce experimental data available, given

the wide range of tests needed to validate criteria [5]. Specifically, there is a lack of reliable data for biaxial stress states both for failure onset and damage propagation. This is especially true for some load ratios which are difficult to enforce in real testing conditions.

These issues are best illustrated in Fig 1a, showing failure data for a biaxial-loaded single layer E-Glass/MY750 Epoxy lamina [5], superimposed with the widely used Tsai-Wu failure envelope [6]; it can be observed that experimental points in the first quadrant (i.e. tension-tension) exhibit poor correlation with the criterion, while those in the fourth quadrant are in relatively good agreement; nevertheless, the criterion offers no information on which failure mode was triggered. Fig 1b shows failure envelopes predicted by LaRC04 failure criterion [2], associated to a phenomenological explanation which accounts for distinct failure modes. This envelope successfully fits experimental data in quadrants 2 and 3, but does not consider possible interactions among the tensile longitudinal and transverse failure modes which might occur in the first quadrant. Thus, reliable experimental data is necessary for understanding such interactions, and for validating (or developing) adequate failure criteria in quadrant 1.

Fig.1. Failure envelopes predicted by a) Tsai-Wu criterion and b) LARc04 criterion

This work focuses on developing an improved specimen for the biaxial testing of fibre-reinforced composite materials, and associated testing procedures, particularly for the tension–tension (e.g. first) quadrant. Section 2 of this paper reviews the state of the art in biaxial specimens for composites. In Section 3, the strain distributions within the gauge section for two different cruciform specimens are analyzed via finite elements (FE). Based on these results, as well as in existing standards and guidelines for the uniaxial testing of metals and composites, Section 4 presents an enhanced cruciform, aiming to ensure that the strain field within the gauge zone (specimen’s central region) remains nearly uniform. Section 5 closes with pertinent concluding remarks.

2. CRUCIFORM SPECIMENS FOR BIAXIAL TESTING

Biaxial stress states were formerly recreated via thin-walled tubes subjected to hydrostatic, axial and torsional loads [7]. However, energy propagation through the wall

thickness and other significant features are misrepresented in non-tubular components. Another disadvantage was pressure leakage after failure onset.

A more representative case of typical industrial scenarios (e.g. flat or gently-curved thin plates subjected to plane stress/strain) [7] is given by a cruciform specimen under orthogonal (i.e. biaxial) loads (Fig. 2a), although testing conditions are not straightforward. For example, stress concentrations at the corners often cause premature failure outside the gauge zone, thus invalidating the test or (even worse) producing wrong information about material's ultimate strength. Some designs address this issue by using different fillet configurations (Fig. 2b).

Fig.2. a) basic cruciform specimen, and b) corner-filletted specimen

One way to enforce failure within the gauge zone is by weakening it via gradual thickness reduction, thus forming a squared depression around specimen's centre [7, 8, 9]. This feature could be machined after the lay-up and curing of the specimen (Fig 3), although this approach would not be recommended for 2D or 3D fabrics. Alternative geometries consist on varying arm-width proportionally to the expected stress/strain field [10]. Other designs featured a circular-windowed gauge zone, still producing early rupture near the thickness-varying zone [11, 12]. The latter references suggested that improving the manufacturing process and using a rhombus shape in the loaded zone could achieve a more uniform strain distribution. Other studies [8] suggest that a larger gauge zone would also help to achieve uniform load transfer without inducing large shear strains.

Fig.3. Squared-windowed specimen lay-up

3. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

To investigate about the reliability of experimental failure data provided by biaxially-loaded cruciform specimen tests, two representative cruciform specimens were modelled via finite elements. Model 1 corresponds to a flat filleted-corners cruciform, while model 2 represents a squared-windowed one. Material employed for both models was unidirectional IM7 carbon fibre/8551-7 epoxy with 0.125mm thickness per layer, which mechanical properties are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Elastic and strength data for unidirectional IM7 Carbon Fiber/ 8551-7 epoxy, Fibre volume V_f (%) 60 [5]

E_1	E_2	E_3	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
(GPa)								
165	8.4	8.4	5.6	5.6	2.8	0.34	0.34	0.5
X_T	X_C	Y_T	Y_C	Z_T	Z_C	S_{12}	S_{13}	S_{23}
(MPa)								
2560	1590	73	185	63	185	90	90	57
ϵ_{1T}	ϵ_{1C}	ϵ_{2T}	ϵ_{2C}	ϵ_{3T}	ϵ_{3C}	γ_{12u}	γ_{13u}	γ_{23u}
(%)								
1.551	1.1	0.87	3.2	0.755	3.2	5	5	2.1

ANSYS® Shell 99 linear layered elements were used for all models. In order to compare strain results, same boundary conditions were applied to all specimens, as shown in Fig.4. Assuming a homogeneous strain distribution along the specimen, a 1:1 biaxial load ratio is sought by enforcing displacements U_x and U_y given by:

$$U_x = \epsilon_{1T} \frac{L}{2} \quad U_y = -\epsilon_{2T} L.$$

Fig.4. Boundary conditions applied to FE models.

3.1 Results

Strains, rather than stresses, were here employed as an assessment tool. This is due to the large longitudinal-to-transverse failure stress ratio (i.e. >35) typically exhibited by unidirectional composite lamina for the considered material, which could easily **override** important stress concentrations. On the other hand, the longitudinal-to-transverse failure strain ratio is less than 2.

Strain results for both models are reported graphically by splitting specimen's geometry in top-right, top-left and bottom sections, corresponding to ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} and γ_{xy} strains, respectively. Notice that a separate scale is used for each. Normalized strain gradients along predefined paths were analyzed, in order to compare the resultant strain fields of both models. Normalization was achieved by expressing strain values as a fraction of their correspondent ultimate strain in a uniaxial test.

Strain results for Model 1 are shown in the Fig.5. In spite of ample fillets, maximum strain values of ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} and γ_{xy} are located precisely near these features. This is in agreement with failed specimens reported in literature [7, 8] causing trenched arms (an unacceptable test). For the same model, Fig. 6 shows normalized strain field gradients along the path defined by line *oa*, having a slope of 45° . Large gradients near the fillet ($r/a=1$) can be observed for all strains. Moreover, ϵ_{yy} remains at near-zero within the gauge zone. This can be explained by the significant difference between longitudinal/transversal stiffness.

Fig.5. Carbon fiber/8551-7 epoxy, single-layer [0], re-entrant filleted specimen. Colour scales represent FE results for ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} and γ_{xy} strains, respectively (all dimensions are given in mm)

Fig.6. Normalized ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} and γ_{xy} strains along path **oa**.

Strain results for Model 2 are shown in Fig. 7. Due to complexities added by new features, two paths - **oa** and **ob**- were defined to monitor gradients in the strain field, shown in Fig. 8. The latter shows that ϵ_{xx} is maximum at the centre of the gauge zone, while ϵ_{yy} reaches a maximum near the top edge of the window. Although this design alleviates stress concentrations at the fillets, it exacerbates those at the top and bottom chamfer's edges. The specimen succeeds in achieving a more uniform biaxial stress state within the gauge zone, but strain gradients are still relatively large.

Fig.7. Carbon fiber/8551-7 epoxy, $[(0/90)_3/0]_S$ square-windowed reinforced specimen [9]
 ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} and γ_{xy} strain results (all dimensions are given in mm)

Fig.8. Normalized ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} and γ_{xy} strains along paths oa and ob .

4. ENHANCED SPECIMEN

Based on results hitherto, an enhanced specimen is here proposed (Fig.10.). The starting point is the squared-windowed specimen, which generates a more homogeneous biaxial strain field. However, it suffers from high transversal strain gradients within the gauge zone, reaching a maximum value near the top and bottom edges of the window. This drawback can be alleviated via a 45° rotation of the squared window, thus having a rhomboidal shape. This enhancement increases the distance between arm and window edges, thus alleviating stress concentrations at these zones. Ample fillets were also added for this end. Another subtle but key enhancement is enforcing same fibre direction in the central (gauge) and adjacent laminas, to avoid spurious strains in the gauge zone due to inter-lamina interactions.

Fig.10. Carbon fiber/8551-7 epoxy, $[90/0/0]_s$ reinforced rhomboid-windowed specimen, strain results (all dimensions are given in mm)

Fig. 11. Normalized ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} and γ_{xy} strains along paths *oa* and *ob* for $[90/0/0]_s$ reinforced rhomboid-windowed sample

Another modification was reducing from six (Model 2 in Section 2) to four the number of reinforcing (top and bottom) laminas; this was done because side analyses (not shown here) indicated that the later configuration produces failure before the biaxial strain field develops large gradients due to longitudinal/transversal interaction. Strain results for the proposed Model are shown in Fig. 11; again, two paths - *oa* and *ob*- were defined to monitor the strain field. The latter shows that ϵ_{xx} remains essentially constant and ϵ_{yy} presents smooth gradients along both paths. The shear strain γ_{xy} remains nearly zero.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Based on comparative analyses between two representative cruciform specimens, an enhanced design is here proposed, with better overall qualities for the biaxial testing of fibre-reinforced composite materials. Key improvements are:

- A main feature of the analyses presented here is that they are strain-based. Optimizations based on levels of stress cannot fully capture the information here revealed. For example, large differences in longitudinal/transversal stiffness can yield similar stresses in both directions, although the strain field can be far from uniform, for which damaging strain concentrations could remain unspotted.
- Despite the use of strain-normalized boundary conditions, the strain ratios revealed values far different than those expected (1:1). This is due to large strain concentrations produced by the thinned gage zone. This effect must be considered for the test program.
- The comparative analyses revealed that typical cruciform specimens develop high strain gradients in the gauge zone and corners, of up to 3 times the theoretical value. During testing, this could produce premature failure and unreliable experimental data which misrepresent the intended stress state.
- It was found that the analyzed specimens do not produce a true biaxial strain field in the gauge zone, **even** when subjected to an equi-biaxial loading condition. This condition would yield totally wrong information about the true ultimate strength, even if failure occurs within the gauge.
- Compared to other designs, the rhomboid-windowed specimen achieved a relatively flat strain field inside the gauge, while keeping a near-zero shear strain. This represents almost ideal biaxial conditions. In spite of those refinements, high values of shear strain near the fillets were observed in the enhanced specimen. This problem will be tackled in future work (currently in progress), via topographical and topological optimization.

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References

- [1] Pinho, S.T.; Iannucci L.; Robinson P. “Physically-based failure models and criteria for laminated fibre-reinforced composites with emphasis on fibre kinking: Part I: Development.” *Composites: Part A* 37 (2006) 63–73.
- [2] Pinho, S.T.; Dávila C.G.; Camanho P.P.; Iannucci L.; Robinson, P. “Failure models and criteria for FRP under in-plane or three-dimensional stress states including shear non-linearity”. Hampton, VA: NASA Langley Research Center, 2005.
- [3] Camanho; P.P.; Dávila C.G.; Pinho, S.T.; Iannucci, L.; Robinson P. “Prediction of in situ strengths and matrix cracking in composites under transverse tension and in-plane shear”. *Composites: Part A* 37 (2006) 165–176.
- [4] Smits, A.; Van Hemelrijck, D.; Philippidis; T.; Van Wingerde, A.M.; Cardon, A. “Study of the usability of various cruciform geometries for biaxial testing of fiber reinforced composites”. XXI International Congress of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics. Warsaw, Poland, August 15-21, 2004.
- [5] Hinton, M.J., Kaddour, A.S., Soden, P.D., “Failure criteria in fibre-reinforced polymer composites: the World-Wide Failure Exercise, a composites science and technology compendium”, Elsevier, 2004.
- [6] Paris, F. “A study of failure criteria of fibrous composite materials”. Hampton, Virginia: George Washington University, Langley Research Center, 2001.
- [7] Van Hemelrijck, D., et al. "Biaxial Testing of Fibre Reinforced Composites." 16th International Conference on Composite Materials. Kyoto: ICCM, 2007.
- [8] Smits, A., Van Hemelrijck, D.; Philippidis, T. P.; Cardon. "Design of a cruciform specimen for biaxial testing of fibre reinforced composite laminates." *Composites Science and Technology*, 2006: 964-975.
- [9] Youssef, Y. “Résistance des composites stratifiés sous chargement biaxial: validation expérimentale des prédictions théoriques”. Thèse de doctorat ès sciences appliquées. Université de Sherbrooke, 1995.
- [10] Bechel, V.T. “Modified Cruciform Test for Application to Graphite/Epoxy Composites”. *Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures*, 2002,9:1, 1 – 17.
- [11] Welsh, Jeffrey S; Adams, Donald F. “An experimental investigation of the biaxial strength of IM6/3501-6 carbon/epoxy cross-ply laminates using cruciform specimens”. *Composites: Part A* 33 (2002) 829-839.
- [12] Sacharuk, Z. “Critères de rupture et optimisation des éléments en matériaux composites”. Thèse de doctorat ès sciences appliquées. Université de Sherbrooke, 1990.